

FORMS OF WORKING WITH PARENTS IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. In this article, the forms of working with parents in elementary grades, organizing a meeting of parents, creating and conducting activities of the class parents' council, working with children with difficult upbringing, and working with students' families are used in this article. traditional and non-traditional methods are discussed.

Keywords: Primary education, student, class leader, parent, parent meeting, parent council, method, traditional and non-traditional methods.

INTRODUCTION

The work of teachers with families is considered a complex and important part of the work of the school's pedagogical team. In particular, class leaders work in parallel with the group of students and their parents in carrying out educational and educational work. His work in cooperation with parents is a special direction of educational work, in which class leaders develop strategies and tactics of cooperation between schools and families aimed at the formation of the child's personality. As a specialist in pedagogy and psychology, he works as a pedagogue-consultant who helps parents on family education issues and corrects the influence of the external environment on the child's personality. That is, the head of the class organizes various forms of work with parents to create a positive environment for the formation of the child's personality.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In cooperation with parents, providing parents with psychological, pedagogical and methodical knowledge, involving parents in the work of the class leader with students, making corrections in the family education of some students, pedagogical tact and deontological norms it is expected to perform functions such as introducing parents to the content of educational activities organized by the school.

RESULTS

In the pedagogical literature, there are four main stages of the class teacher's work with parents:

Working with parents of primary school students.

Working with parents of 5th graders (adjusting the transition to primary school).

Work with parents of primary school students (grades 6-8). Working with parents of high school and graduate students.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Parents and schools working as partners can only increase pupil achievement and help to develop positive attitudes about self and school.

We aim to:

Be a welcoming and friendly school for parents/carers and visitors.

Establish a mutually supportive and respectful relationship with all of our parents where trust and clear communication is at the heart of all we do.

Keep parents informed and involved in a positive way, through working in partnership together in order to help every pupil achieve their full potential socially, emotionally and academically.

Respond swiftly and efficiently to the needs of parent callers and visitors.

Provide timely and relevant information for parents through the use of our text messaging service, school website, the email distribution of letters and newsletters.

·Bring pupils' learning to life for parents via Class Dojo/Tapestry.

The school would like an effective partnership with parents by valuing your help in the following ways:

Coming to school on time both at the beginning and end of the day

Getting to know your child's teacher so that you can share in their achievements and concerns

Making an appointment if you need to talk at length about your child

Attending all Parents Meetings/Curriculum workshops

Reading at home daily with your child and taking an interest in homework

Reading all letters that your child brings home

Keeping us informed of any changes to circumstances which may affect your child in school

Our experience and research show that an effective partnership with parents is reflected in a more successful performance by children at school. We do make mistakes and there are misunderstandings but these can be reduced to a minimum if we keep in close contact and work together to put things right.

CONCLUSIONS

At any stage, the cooperation between the head of the class and the family begins with the study of family educational conditions and microclimate, individual characteristics of children and parents. A class teacher is given a lesson to work for several years. He doesn't know any of the children or their parents at all yet, so he must gather as much information as possible about his students' families, get to know the students themselves, the family's lifestyle, he should understand its customs and traditions, spiritual values, the style of relations between parents and children. All

this is necessary for the proper planning of educational work in the classroom with maximum efficiency.

In conclusion, it is worth mentioning that every meeting we have with parents arouses the desire to think, analyze and reason. Recently, parent meetings need to be held in a new way. Our parent meetings should consist of pedagogical education, counseling, discussion and family celebrations. Because such methods allow parents to actively participate in the meeting.

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